

Case Study Report for “The Infinite Index: Information Retrieval on Generative Text-To-Image Models”

NIKLAS DECKERS, Leipzig University and ScaDS.AI, Germany

MAIK FRÖBE, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Germany

JOHANNES KIESEL, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar, Germany

GIANLUCA PANDOLFO, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar, Germany

CHRISTOPHER SCHRÖDER, Leipzig University, Germany

BENNO STEIN, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar, Germany

MARTIN POTTHAST, Leipzig University and ScaDS.AI, Germany

This report accompanies the following paper:

Niklas Deckers, Maik Fröbe, Johannes Kiesel, Gianluca Pandolfo, Christopher Schröder, Benno Stein, and Martin Potthast. The Infinite Index: Information Retrieval on Generative Text-To-Image Models. 2023 Conference on Human Information Interaction & Retrieval (CHIIR 2023). March 2023. ACM

Weblink: https://webis.de/publications.html#deckers_2023a

WARNING. This report contains depictions of skulls and undead fantasy creatures.

The report uses the notation [a;b] to note that the observed behavior indicates the search task a of Kuhltau’s Information Search Process model and the task of resource usage b. Queries are shown as “query”.

The artwork search started with the following description of the desired artwork. The professional was asked to confirm the statement every 30 minutes. The statement did not change during the case study.

A deck-building online card game like “Magic the Gathering” set in a fantasy universe. Players would choose one from several “leader” cards that would determine their “faction”—other cards available to them for building their deck. Illustrations for each faction would be visually coherent, but different factions could have different color palettes and symbols. Illustrations could be similar to those used in “Magic the Gathering” and have a level of detail like typical concept art.

Authors’ addresses: Niklas Deckers, niklas.deckers@uni-leipzig.de, Leipzig University and ScaDS.AI, Center for Scalable Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence, Dresden/Leipzig, Germany; Maik Fröbe, maik.froebe@uni-jena.de, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Jena, Germany; Johannes Kiesel, johannes.kiesel@uni-weimar.de, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar, Weimar, Germany; Gianluca Pandolfo, gianluca.pandolfo@uni-weimar.de, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar, Weimar, Germany; Christopher Schröder, christopher.schroeder@uni-leipzig.de, Leipzig University, Leipzig, Germany; Benno Stein, benno.stein@uni-weimar.de, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar, Weimar, Germany; Martin Potthast, martin.pothast@uni-leipzig.de, Leipzig University and ScaDS.AI, Center for Scalable Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence, Dresden/Leipzig, Germany.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution International 4.0 License. Unless otherwise noted, images should be attributed to “Webis”.

1 COLLECTING THE MOOD BOARD

The professional describes they first look what others did. He first uses the “Community Feed” in the Midjourney web app (without query) to browse images created by other Midjourney users,¹ which shows images (including prompts and process history) posted on the Midjourney Discord server.

He says he is looking for possible art styles, compositions, and characters [selection; support creative process]. He uses the bookmark feature of the web interface to tag each image he found to be relevant with respect to one of these dimensions [selection; manage found information]. Images the professional bookmarks (without looking at the prompt) include:

Left image by dinesh75000, center and right image by WEIRDHAUS; Images owned by their authors

¹<https://www.midjourney.com/app/feed/all/>; Access requires a free Midjourney (Discord) account. The Midjourney model version is “v3”.

The professional then used the “Styles” in the Midjourney web app (without query) to browse specifically for artist styles to use as part of his future prompts [selection; learn domain knowledge].

He expected he would be able to see images generated with some style by clicking on it, but nothing happened.

So he instead went back to the community feed and issued the query “fantasy; concept art; magic the gathering; artstation” [selection; support creative process]. The first three terms were chosen according to the game statement (see above). The last term was chosen as a reference to the art web page <https://www.artstation.com>, as the professional heard many users of Midjourney add this term for high-quality artwork. The professional mentioned he is specifically looking for images with interesting lighting and drama [selection; support creative process]. He continued to bookmark images. When he noticed that several images were created by the same user, he clicked on that user’s name to also have a look at other images of that user [selection; support creative process]. Images the professional bookmarks (without looking at the prompt) include:

Left and right image by WEIRDHAUS, center image by NFTbutterfly; Images owned by their authors

He went through all results for his query (about 100) without looking at the prompts. He had expected more images. He then scrolled back to the start of the list and clicked on some of the bookmarked images to learn the prompt for that image and see whether the images shared part of their prompts [exploration; learn domain knowledge].

Still looking for more images, he generalized the query to “magic the gathering” and expected to get similar images, just more [selection; support creative process]. He thus remarked he was happy he saw some images he already knew [selection; learn procedural knowledge]. He further remarked he was now looking at single elements in the images that might be interesting his game [exploration; support creative process]. Images the professional bookmarks include:

Left image by dangelo, center image by subomega, right image by Cbass; Images owned by their authors

The professional then encountered an image that depicts playing cards.

Image by Art_Of_AI; Image owned by its author

Intrigued, he bookmarks it and reads its prompt to learn how to produce such card images [exploration; learn domain knowledge]. With this knowledge, he uses the query “card design” to the community feed to see more examples of images using these words in their prompt, in order to see different card designs to choose from [selection; specific information]. He notices that most images look like Tarot cards, but he still likes them and bookmarks several in case he needs them later. He remarks these could be back-side images for the cards. Images the professional bookmarks include:

Left image by Mesako, center and right image by OotavidMann; Images owned by their authors

Seeing the different images next to each other, he remarks that these could be the symbols of the different factions. He then checks his bookmarks in the web interface and un-bookmarks a few images that do not fit to the others in terms of colors and style [exploration; manage found information]. He further remarks that it would be helpful for him to order and group the images to check that the relevant ones fit together.

He further investigates his bookmarks, looking for common elements and what could be missing [exploration; manage found information].

Noticing that artwork for “creatures” is missing, he uses the query “concept art; magic the gathering; creatures” to find these [formulation; specific information]. Images the professional bookmarks include:

Left image by timo.noack, center image by Fabio [Polygonmaker], right image by M A G O; Images owned by their authors

The professional then checks his bookmarks page again to see if the images are coherent and that he has gathered artwork for different types of cards. He is satisfied with what he has and says this bookmark page fulfills his requirements for a mood board. It is shown in full on the next side. Creating this mood board took about 30 minutes.

The professional then consults his mood board to pick a first faction to create cards for [initiation; support creative process]. He looks at the bookmarked images in detail and reads their prompts [selection; learn domain knowledge].

2 CREATING THE UNDEAD RIDER

Inspired by the following picture he decides to create a faction that centers on necromancy and undead creatures.

Image by M A G O; Image owned by its author

Its prompt reads: “Nightly darkness creatures riding from the depths of earth, digital painting, matte painting, midjourney, concept art, detailed art, scifiart cinematic painting, magic the Gathering, volumetric light, masterpiece, volumetric realistic render, epic scene, 8k, post-production detailed art, scifiart cinematic painting.”

He edits the prompt [exploration; support creative process]. Before sending, he checks the “User Manual” in the “Help & FAQ” section of the web interface for parameters [exploration; learn procedural knowledge]. He decides to add “--q 2” to increase the image quality.

“necromancer riding a horse in nightly darkness in the depths of earth, digital painting, matte painting, midjourney, concept art, detailed art, scifiart cinematic painting, magic the Gathering, volumetric light, masterpiece, volumetric realistic render, epic scene, 8k, post-production detailed art, scifiart cinematic painting --q 2”

He waits for the images to be generated, then studies them in detail. He iteratively selects the one that looks most promising to him and uses the “variations” feature to create similar images [formulation; specific information].

He then uses the ‘upscale’ feature to create a version of his favourite image with higher resolution [collection; support creative process].

He checks if variations of the upscaled image would improve further.

As this is not the case, he decides to instead test also the other two supported and suggested upscaling algorithms for whether they change the image composition and drama [collection; specific information]:

He is quite satisfied with the results, though he finds them a bit dark. He wonders if he could use the model to lighten up the image. So he uses “light up --iw 2” and includes a reference to the previously generated image. “--iw 2” specifies

that the image should be weighed twice as much as the textual prompt [formulation; learn procedural knowledge]. However, kind of what he expected, the result are quite different images:

He then marks his favourite image by tagging it with a smiley-emoji. He does so as there is only one bookmark list available and that one he already used for his mood board [presentation; manage found information].

Having checked that he can easily re-find the tagged images by sorting his “Home”-view by “Hot,” he remarks that the image is not a necromancer as he intended and expected, but he is still satisfied with the result. He states that he “also wanted to be surprised.” He further states that at he is not clear whether he will use the image for a card in the final game. Rather, he says he intends to create himself a “library” of images to then choose from.

Creating the undead rider took him about 25 minutes.

3 CREATING THE ZOMBIE HORDE

He then decides to create a “zombie horde” image. He again copies the prompt from an image in his bookmarks and edits it [exploration; support creative process]. He hopes that the re-use of keywords leads to a consistent image style.

“a horde of zombies wandering through a swampy area in the middle of the night, it is full moon and autumn, desaturated landscape, magic the gathering, fantasy art, de-noise, 4K, --ar 4:3 --test --creative --upbeta”

The prompt uses the (at that time) new “--test --creative” model, which produces more “realistic” images according to the documentation. He does not like the result, saying it is not detailed enough and that the composition is bad, and decides to strip the corresponding parameters and some other parts of the prompt to sharpen it to the core description [exploration; specific information]:

“a horde of zombies wandering through a swampy area in the middle of the night, it is full moon and autumn, magic the gathering, fantasy art, 4k, --ar 4:3”

He then again tries to generalize the prompt: “a horde of zombies wandering through a swampy area in the middle of the night, it is full moon, magic the gathering, fantasy art, 4K, --ar 4:3” [exploration; specific information]. He tries this prompt two times:

He likes some of the results (especially the drama), and then again uses “variations” to generate similar images in the hope to find a better one [formulation; specific information].

He remarks it would be helpful to have a way to pin the current favourite image, as he tries to re-find an image he created earlier [formulation; manage found information].

He again uses the different “upscales” on his favourite image, trying to describe the results as they are created. He finds the surprising results of the upscalings “unpleasant” [collection; specific informaton]. He confirms by test that upscaling produces different results if run again [collection; learn procedural knowledge].

He then uses the “remaster” function out of curiosity [exploration; learn procedural knowledge]. This feature uses the new “--test --creative” parameters when creating the upscale.

He says he likes that the “remastered” looks quite different, though he would thus not use it. He also says he clearly will post-process the images in Photoshop. However, he is satisfied with the result so far.

4 CREATING THE ZOMBIE ATTACK

He then decides to create an action scene for an event card or similar. He again looks at his bookmarks / mood board to copy a prompt [exploration; support creative process]. He would like to have a feature that allows him to store and quickly re-use parts of the prompt.

“zombie creature crawls out of a sewer, attacks human person, foggy night, dramatic light, digital painting, matte painting, midjourney, concept art, detailed art, sci-fi cinematic painting, magic the Gathering, volumetric light, masterpiece, volumetric realistic render, epic scene, 8k, post-production detailed art, sci-fi cinematic painting --q 2”

He again generates variations iteratively [formulation; specific information].

He again uses the different upscales and the remaster for fine-tuning [collection; specific informaton].

And tries once more to create a variation, but is then satisfied with the previous result.

He says he had imagined the image to be different at the start, with some undead hand grabbing a human at their leg, so he is somewhat disappointed that the human is missing on the images. However, he said his main concern was the idea of a zombie attack, and the generated images clearly fulfill this requirement.

He then takes a look at the newly generated image next to the chosen image for the undead rider. After a careful inspection, he says he believes that they are alright and especially have a coherent style. [presentation; manage found informaton]

5 CREATING THE UNDEAD LEADER

He then decides to generate a “leader” card for the faction. He this time looks directly at the prompts of the bookmarked images to gather keywords and parameters for his prompt [exploration; support creative process]:

“Dark Lord, heavy armor with skulls, holding a sword, character concept, fantasy, atmospheric, beautiful, hyper real, insane details, matte, sharp focus, cinematic, octane render, high quality illustration, 8k, digital painting, magic the gathering, gwent, artgerm, artstation, DeviantArt, in the art style of Luisa Preissler, Magali Villeneuve, greg rutkowski, Donato Giancola, Howard Lyon, Daarken, Gerald brom, Anna Podedworna, Todd Lockwood, Artem demura --ar 2:3 --q 2 --v 3”

He remarks the results do not look like a leader and changes parts of the prompt [exploration; support creative process]:

“commander of dark legions, heavy black armor with a lot of skulls, holding a dagger, character concept, fantasy, atmospheric, beautiful, hyper real, insane details, matte, sharp focus, cinematic, octane render, high quality illustration, 8k, digital painting, magic the gathering, gwent, artgerm, artstation, DeviantArt, in the art style of Luisa Preissler, Magali Villeneuve, greg rutkowski, Donato Giancola, Howard Lyon, Daarken, Gerald brom, Anna Podedworna, Todd Lockwood, Artem demura --ar 2:3 --q 2 --v 3”

Though he likes the composition of that image more, he still thinks it deviates too much from his previous results, so he decides to add images that he already generated to the prompt [exploration; specific information]. He tries two times:

prompt text +

→

prompt text +

→

He comments that “it is obvious they [Midjourney] have Cosplay poses” in their training data set. He especially likes the results for the second attempt and again starts to create variations, remasters, and upscales [formulation/collection; specific information].

He then remarks it would be good to search for names of “Magic the Gathering” artists. He does so using Google search [selection; learn domain knowledge]: “10 best magic the gathering illustrators”. He goes to one list page in

the results and finds that there is a large overlap with the prompt he copied. He is satisfied with that, but thinks the generated images are too blurry. He continues to create variations [formulation; specific information].

However, he is not fully satisfied, remarking that he would like to change the mood. So he changes the prompt slightly by adding “night time, foggy scenario” and adds the image he liked most to the prompt, creating two new sets of images [formulation; specific information]: “commander of dark legions, heavy black armor with a lot of skulls, holding a dagger, night time, foggy scenario, rim light, character concept, fantasy, atmospheric, beautiful, hyper real, insane details, matte, sharp focus, cinematic, octane render, high quality illustration, 8k, digital painting, magic the gathering, gwent, artgerm, artstation, DeviantArt, in the art style of Luisa Preissler, Magali Villeneuve, greg rutkowski, Donato Giancola, Howard Lyon, Daarken, Gerald brom, Anna Podedworna, Todd Lockwood, Artem demura --ar 2:3 --q 2 --v 3”.

prompt text +

→

He then tries a variation of one of the created images [exploration; specific information].

But since he is not satisfied with the result, he rather decides to take the image he previously used as part of the prompt.

6 END OF DAY I

After 2 hours the professional decided to stop generating more images, feeling exhausted. He then used the page in the Midjourney web app to have another look at what he created so far. He quickly switched the setting to showing only upscaled images, stating he could not bear to now look at all generated images. “You get crazy.” “It is simply too much.” He said he felt so exhausted from keeping all images in mind and from intensive mental work to decide what to try next. He explicitly cites the lack of control as a reason for the decisions being that much effort.

To recover, he decides to have a look at the generated images of one other user of whom he had bookmarked an image. He found it interesting to see their failures and successes, stating that getting a good image “is a lucky shot.” Therefore, he suggests, one has to generate many images, but the number of images quickly get overwhelming unless one has a clear artistic vision to quickly sort out images.

He then notices how aspects of creatures in his generated images can also be found in the images of the other user.

At the end of day 1, the professional had generated the following 4 images that he judged as of sufficient quality for his purposes and the best of their group:

7 CREATING THE NATURE ARTIFACTS

The professional starts on the second day with the wish to explore a different faction. However, they decide to keep much of the previously used prompt in order to ensure a cohesive style. He decides on a faction with nature theme (thematic opposite of the undead) and wants to create an artifact. He chooses to create a dagger [exploration; specific information]:

“an ancient golden dagger lying on moss, illuminated by godrays, close up, digital painting, matte painting, midjourney, concept art, detailed art, scifiart cinematic painting, magic the Gathering, volumetric light, masterpiece, volumetric realistic render, epic scene, 8k, post-production detailed art, scifiart cinematic painting --q 2”

He then creates variations by always picking the image he likes best so far. He states he is looking for something consistent with the images he has so far, that looks like a dagger, and lies on the moss [formulation; specific information].

He then tries to upscale the most promising one twice [collection; specific information]

However, he thinks the images do not fit the style of the others he has. So he goes back to his bookmarked images and copies the prompt from there, also changing the dagger description. Furthermore, he adds the image he copied the prompt from to his own prompt, hoping he would get something of similar style [exploration; specific information]. “a medieval dagger lying on moss, lit by god rays, art by Adrian Smith + Paul bonner, magic gathering style, warcraft, blizzard style, hearthstone, fantasy concept art, medieval, masterpiece, mystical,witchcraft”

prompt text +

Image by dangelo; Image owned by its author

→

He thinks the style is closer, and assumes that upscaling makes it even more consistent [collection; specific information].

He really likes the result, and is not troubled by it not being a dagger. He argues that, in the end, he wants interesting artwork that evokes a story for a card. Though he is already quite satisfied, he wants to see what else to find in the

model and creates variations [exploration; support creative process] and more upscales (using the other two algorithms) of the previous images [collection; specific information].

Now he notices that the variations contain actual daggers, and upscales them [collection; specific information]:

He decides to select the first and last upscaled image of this series, saying they evoke a story of two fragments of something larger, which would then inspire game mechanics of the two cards.

8 CREATING THE WEAPON COLLECTION

For the next image he would like to see a set of weapons. He keeps again part of the prompt and updates the content [exploration; specific information].

“medieval weapons on a wooden table, behind a castle wall, camera view from top, volumetric lighting, art by Adrian Smith + Paul bonner, magic gathering style, warcraft, blizzard style, hearthstone, fantasy concept art, medieval, masterpiece, mystical,witchcraft”

He then thinks that “behind” might suggest to the model that it should not be visible and changes the prompt to “in front of” [exploration; specific information].

“medieval weapons on a wooden table, in front of a castle wall, camera view from top, volumetric lighting, art by Adrian Smith + Paul bonner, magic gathering style, warcraft, blizzard style, hearthstone, fantasy concept art, medieval, masterpiece, mystical,witchcraft”

He thinks the castle is too dominant in the image and thus removes it from the prompt [exploration; specific information].

“medieval weapons on a wooden table, in front of a wall, camera view from top, art by Adrian Smith + Paul bonner, magic gathering style, warcraft, blizzard style, hearthstone, fantasy concept art, medieval, masterpiece, mystical,witchcraft --q2”

Still not satisfied, he tries to simplify the prompt, asking himself whether he needs the camera to get “better” results. He also notices that the generated images look sufficiently like in a castle setting, even without the word in the prompt [exploration; specific information].

“medieval weapons on a wooden table, in front of a wall, art by Adrian Smith + Paul bonner, magic gathering style, warcraft, blizzard style, hearthstone, fantasy concept art, medieval, masterpiece, mystical,witchcraft --q 2”

He finds the results interesting, though not necessarily relevant. He still creates variations and upscales in an attempt to better understand the problem [collection; learn domain knowledge].

He sees that in one of the upscaled images the model tried to generate “Magic the Gathering” cards on the table, instead of using it as style. He is uncertain what to do, stating “this leads nowhere” and “if this is not going somewhere, I’ll change the prompt.” Being asked whether he thinks he could change the direction with his action (since he used the location metaphor himself), he answered “No,” and adds, after some thinking “there is a direction, but I have not much influence on it.”

To get inspiration, he then repeats the prompt with “--chaos 100,” which, according to the Midjourney documentation he read on day 1, specifies “How much more varied, random, and different the results will be. Must be between 0-100. Higher values will favor more interesting and unusual generations in exchange for less reliable compositions.” [exploration; support creative process]

The bottom right picture catches his attention, and creates a series of upscales, variations, and remastered versions of it in quick succession [formulation; specific information]:

After the generation, he takes another look at the results [collection; manage information]. He likes some of the results, stating that some of these both fit style-wise with the other picked images and have sufficient interesting elements to tell a story. When he wants to decide which one to pick, he quickly boils it down to two images, but the two are rather far apart in both the Discord- and the web-interface. He says the possibility to tag and filter, or at least move images around in the interface would be very helpful. He then picks the second upscaled images, still using the emoticon-rating, and checks once more on his favourite page that this image fits to the other picked ones.

9 CREATING THE POTION

He again keeps part of the prompt and only changes the content, this time with the goal to create the image of a magic potion [exploration; specific information].

“goblin brewing green poison in a vial, in a goblin laboratory, dramatic scene, illuminated in green, art by Adrian Smith + Paul bonner, magic gathering style, warcraft, blizzard style, hearthstone, fantasy concept art, medieval, masterpiece, mystical, witchcraft --q 2”

This time he likes the first result already a lot. Asked what he thinks makes the difference, he says that he thinks he gets better results when the different parts of the prompt (style and content) fit together. He then creates many variations and upscales in rapid succession [formulation; specific information].

For the last images he remarks that he now also selects images for variations and upscales based on his curiosity on the result, as these images do not really fit the style of his picked images [formulation; learn procedural knowledge]. He thinks for several minutes which one to pick, and then chooses the one below. Though he remarks he would especially for this one like to do some post-processing in Adobe's Photoshop and maybe change a few things using DALL·E's in-painting method. But not right now.

10 CREATING THE UNDEAD BANNER

For the last card to be created in the study he decides he wants to try out something different and create a banner for the undead faction, that could serve as the backside of that faction's cards. He copies a rather short command from a card image in his bookmarks and does minor modifications [exploration; specific information].

"tarot card design, ornate, satanism, skull, god of death
--ar 2:3"

He then tries to minimize the prompt [exploration; learn procedural knowledge].

“banner,god of death, ornate, satanism, skull --ar 2:3”

He likes the results, but says it is clear he has to define the style to make it coherent to what he already picked. So he copies that part of the prompt [exploration; specific information].

“banner,god of death, ornate, satanism, skull, fantasy, atmospheric, beautiful, hyper real, insane details, matte, sharp focus, cinematic, octane render, high quality illustration, 8k, digital painting, magic the gathering, gwent, artgerm, artstation, DeviantArt, in the art style of Luisa Preissler, Magali Villeneuve, greg rutkowski, Donato Giancola, Howard Lyon, Daarken, Gerald brom, Anna Podedworna, Todd Lockwood, Artem demura --ar 2:3”

He likes the results and upscales them, though he remarks they are not what he wanted as they do not look like banners. He says he would like to have a “might be relevant for another project”-button.

So he goes back to his bookmarks and copies the prompts from another card image [exploration; specific information].

“black paper + tarot card + skull + vintage detailed fantasy illustration designed by Marc Simonetti and Mike Mignola + psychedelic black light style + intricate ink illustration + silver pearl filigree + red + symmetry --ar 2:3 ”

He again creates variations as he likes several of these [formulation; specific information].

He then looks at the generated images again to see which ones to upscale, remarking reasons for not doing so like “looks too alien,” “looks to maya-like,” or “looks to crazy.” He decides on two images to upscale [collection; specific information]:

He picks the left one.

11 END OF DAY II

At the end, the professional makes some conclusions on the uses of text-to-image generation.

- It is much faster, especially when copying prompts from someone else; especially suited to define a look-and-feel, compositions, and color palette.
- Especially useful for concept art, where one can let oneself be led to interesting compositions and does not have to re-create an image from mind.
- It is also especially nice for a card game, as some images contain weird elements that people will not see on the rather small cards.
- He is surprised how aesthetically pleasing the images are, even though they are not that delicate.

The picked images are:

